

Challenges of Teaching Physics Online During the COVID-19 Pandemic

Ediho Lokanga

Birmingham Metropolitan College,
Birmingham, United Kingdom.
Email: Ediho.Lokanga@bmet.ac.uk

1. Introduction

In March 2020, most governments worldwide, including the United Kingdom (UK), made the brave decision to close schools, colleges, and universities due to the coronavirus disease 2019 pandemic. During the pandemic, students moved online to complete their education. The COVID-19 pandemic brought with it countless problems, including several challenges in many fields such as the economy, health, politics, transport, logistics and education. The pandemic affected the global economy in a way we have not seen in over 50 years. It disrupted the entire education sector. Ametepe and Khan (2021) document some of these challenges: faculty-specific challenges (adjusting their teaching methods and materials to an online format), student challenges (mental health issues and adjusting to a new way of learning), technology challenges (lack of infrastructure and limited access to the internet) etc.

The unexpected disruptions to schools, colleges and universities made everyone aware of the need to implement new ways of teaching and delivering lessons online. The pandemic struck unexpectedly, and there was no time for preparation; everyone had to function as quickly as possible and adapt to online learning and teaching. Some institutions or colleges successfully provided e-learning platforms or other digital learning management systems to support students and themselves. However, not all were successful in doing so, and others did not do so, as rightly pointed out by Almahasees et al. (2021). The lack of access to education for all creates barriers to learning; Dewsbury and Brame (2019) discuss the need for inclusive learning and how to support students. Further, Vygotsky (1978) argues that social integration plays a vital role in students' learning ability. We learn from the zones of proximal development that students' ability to problem-solving is enhanced with the support of more capable peers.

The UK has one of the most excellent digital infrastructures globally. As such, there is no issue of accessibility for much of the population. The 2020 statistic from the government published by Statista (2020) shows that 97% of the total population has access to the internet. Despite higher accessibility, the scope of online classes for formal education was limited before COVID-19. Although most schools are well and fully equipped with the latest hardware and software such as presentation tools, computer simulations software, animation software and online platforms software, they were primarily used for regular classes or laboratory activities before the pandemic.

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused so much damage to our society. Klein et al. (2020) suggest the damages are irreparable and will take several years to fix. Although these disruptions were felt in teaching various subjects,

teaching and learning physics online has been challenging and created a lot of new issues in a topic that has seen a decrease in the number of students taking it worldwide. Abtokhi, Jatmiko and Wasis (2021) rightly point out that increasingly complex obstacles were displayed in learning physics online. They concluded that physics teaching and learning could not be taught effectively through online media. I partially disagree with their findings and believe that many aspects of physics can be successfully taught online. However, I acknowledge that it is not easy to replace face-to-face laboratory experiments, even with online laboratories and simulations. I witnessed this with BTEC Applied science (physics) students at Matthew Boulton College.

Therefore, this study aims to provide insights into the challenges faced by teachers and students, including associated technological issues, during the pandemic and its effects on colleges' teaching and learning process. This study also evaluates the teaching and learning of physics during the COVID-19 pandemic. Therefore, the findings of this document will help us answer several questions, help teachers improve their online courses during the COVID-19 pandemic and, most importantly, future online and face-to-face courses post-pandemic.

To discuss the challenges disruptions during the pandemic and the way forward, I would like to address the following four questions.

- What were the challenges met by teachers or lecturers during their online physics teaching, and how did they address them?
- Also, are there issues that learners met? How did they address them?
- What were the technical issues encountered by both learners and teachers?
- Have new teaching methodologies or practices been created in response to the COVID-19 pandemic?

The motivation of this paper is presented in the introduction, followed by the four sections. A contextual literature review about the related challenges, including associated information and communication technology (ICT) issues, faced by educators and students is performed in section two. In section three, I discuss the methods used to collect data, pointing out their strengths and weaknesses. And in section four, I analyse the data collected by several researchers, focusing on four papers. Finally, the paper closes with a conclusion and recommendations for further work.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Online Teaching and Learning

Online teaching or web-based education has grown over the last twenty years, so most universities now offer online degrees or blended learning. Several authors have designed a guideline for developing and creating an online learning environment. For instance, Garrison et al. (2021) find three essential elements: social presence, cognitive presence and teaching presence. Kang and Seo (2021) tell us that social presence refers to learners feeling like part of the learning community, not outsiders. In comparison, they argue that cognitive presence relates to students' participation in inquiry. And lastly, teaching presence includes identifying students' learning, giving feedback, peer-to-peer collaboration, involvement in the learning experience etc. These are the minimum requirements for an effective online learning environment.

Undoubtedly, the development of ICT has created several opportunities to develop new forms of teaching and learning. Abtokhi et al. (2021) discuss how using technology during the pandemic has greatly benefited education and provided more effective and accessible learning experiences. Many of these new online teaching platforms have been inspired by Anderson's (2008) philosophy regarding how effective learning environments, including online learning environments, should be built mainly around four components: learners-centred, knowledge-centred, assessment-centred and community-centred.

Despite the benefits of ICT in teaching and learning and the development of physics web-based online platforms, teachers and learners faced several challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic. In the following lines, I discuss some of these problems.

2.1.1 Teacher challenges

The sudden transition to online teaching meant that teachers had to quickly adapt to a new delivery model. That created several challenges, particularly in the use of technology. These include using new online platforms, developing teaching materials adapted to the unfamiliar environment, delivering the content and engaging students in a virtual environment. These unexpected challenges were not without problems. Tugirinshuti, Mugabo and Banuza (2021) point out that some teachers lacked support from faculty and administration. The same line of reasoning is supported by the work of Ametepe and Khan (2021).

2.1.2 Student challenges

Students, like the wider community, were unprepared and encountered several issues such as learning on a new platform, adjusting mentally, focusing during the online lesson, facing new assessment formats, dealing with ICT issues such as the ability of all students to have access to a computer and the internet and dealing with the pandemic and other problems associated with it.

2.1.3 ICT and laboratory challenges

A typical physics course in the UK consists of lecture sessions, problem-solving sessions and laboratory experiments. So, during COVID-19, these three sessions could not be conducted face to face. For instance, problem solving is a time to bring students together in a small group to tackle problem-solving skills, which leads to students applying critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Although occasional homework focused on problem-solving skills was given, it usually culminated with a discussion with the teacher in the classroom.

Another vital tool for physics learning is the laboratory, where experiments are conducted. Luckily enough, even before the advent of the COVID-19 pandemic, virtual physics laboratory environments had been developed. Among the few Raspberry Pi, see, for instance, Waite (2021) for an in-depth review and virtual laboratory such as PhET (designed by the University of Colorado Boulder). For example, Reagan (2012) and de Jong et al. (2013) highlight the benefits of using them, saying that it enhances the learning process and positively affects cognitive, behavioural and affective learning outcomes, thus embracing Tyler's (1949) linear product or objective model. However, several authors, including Kang and Seo (2021), insist that new, robust, reliable virtual remote laboratories could not be designed, constructed or accessed during the pandemic despite these achievements.

3. Methodology

This article is based on secondary data. The search engines Google and Google Scholar collected data from books, peer-reviewed journals and research papers on Academia, ResearchGate and several other websites. Some articles were collected from educational institutions' websites. Some of these institutions published data on their websites. Alternatively, some of them choose to post in a peer-reviewed journal. After careful analysis, I selected the most relevant articles and left others that I thought were not pertinent to my paper. I checked the originality to gain information from authentic, reliable, trusted websites. I compared articles to get valuable and relevant data, an approach recommended by Long-Sutehall (2010) and Flick (2018).

I gave priority to scholarly and peer-reviewed journals, as they have reports of high original research or experimentation. Scholars in a specialised field wrote them. For accuracy, originality and relevancy, peer-reviewed articles are reviewed by other experts in the same area. All these data collected will be applied to the specific research context to answer questions. These data are from various sources. Both quantitative data and qualitative data from secondary sources were collected. Quantitative data collected were online questionnaires, surveys and reports. On the other side, qualitative data consisted of previous interviews. For instance, questionnaires and surveys are essential for gaining people's opinions, attitudes, inclinations, and perceptions on some issues. They are helpful because they give us quantitative data that can be collated systematically. On the other hand, qualitative data have the advantage of open-ended responses.

Another advantage of qualitative data, such as interviews, is that they give one rich qualitative information about facts and individual experiences and attitudes, as stressed by Specht (2019, p.142). They allow you to follow up, seek clarification, discuss further etc. I carefully analysed the origins of all data collected. I used keyword searches to narrow my search, using several combinations of different keywords. Also, I used citations to locate references to find critical papers and similar publications. I focused on four out of over 30 articles that I downloaded and dug deeper into the challenges that physics teachers faced and those learning physics online during the pandemic.

The paper by Klein et al. (2020) consists of 18 semi-structured interviews and another set of questionnaires, including 246 technical data fields. The questionnaire focused on the learners' attitudes to online learning, communication abilities, technological and social aspects, self-organisation and physics laboratories. On the other hand, Ametepe and Khan (2021) use a survey to gather the challenges that affected students during pandemic-era online teaching and find the strategies that worked. The survey, composed of two questionnaires, was distributed to 161 students at Georgia Gwinnet college who took physics.

Another study led by Delgado (2021) uses mixed research: a quantitative approach supplemented with complementary information from systematic observation and interpretation. Data were collected and recovered from Canvas and Zoom interactions. For every session, a video story was recorded and reviewed. The tutorial was delivered via Zoom, and students had to attend two examinations: homework and teamwork. The fourth paper by Kang and Seo (2021) examines how teachers in a high school conducted themselves in online teaching and the challenges they faced compared to their usual face-to-face teaching during the pandemic.

4. Data Analysis

First, Klein et al. (2020) show that students' learning success is linked with their self-organisation abilities. The data also show that access to friendly study environments and communication with peers and lecturers were key to success. Also, the result indicates that learners who had a positive attitude toward online learning achieved a better grade. In this research, regarding online simulation, which replaced the in-person laboratories, students responded that the online laboratory was less effective in acquiring experiment skills in their first academic year. In contrast, in their second year of exposure to the online laboratory, students were very much more receptive to the idea of online simulation and commented that it helped them acquire practical skills.

Second, the work of Ametepe and Khan (2021) suggests that students liked the idea of working in small groups, called breakrooms, and said that it helped them bond and feel part of the team; they reported it was a gratifying experience. This theme agrees with Vygotsky's (1978) concept of social integration. Additionally, students felt free to ask their teachers questions and received immediate feedback through the chat option or by asking live questions. Those students who had IT issues received support and help throughout the sessions.

This research addressed and focused too much on students; in due course, it failed to consider or involve teachers and their view on challenges they went through. It may be that the researchers took a student-centred approach, an approach to teaching advocated by Rogers (1994) and chose instead to focus on students. I firmly believe that the scholars missed an excellent opportunity to query the lecturers and discuss the kind of challenges they went through. Did they get any support from their faculty? What could have been done to improve their online experiences? These are the questions left unanswered.

From the work of Delgado (2021), we learn that there was a drop in attendance due to several issues, such as the lack of access to the computer, lack of access to reliable means of communication (the internet) and other possible problems. For instance, the drop-off in attendance was 7% higher on average compared to face-to-face a year before COVID-19. Other issues such as health emergencies and the lack of electricity were pointed out. But we note that despite the electricity issue, all the lessons were recorded, giving all students the opportunities to access learning materials anytime and anywhere they wanted. Students responded positively to recorded videos of problem-solving and the ability to access the material anywhere.

Reflecting and analysing the work of Kang and Seo (2021) on student engagement in learning, connecting physics models to everyday phenomenon and model testing. The following consensus appears to emerge. All the eight teachers involved in the consultation were concerned about the lack of face-to-face lessons and how to engage students. They made sure that students had enough work to keep them engaged.

For instance, four of the teachers who only used recorded lecture videos found it challenging to know the effect of their teaching. They could not track whether their students had completed any assignment or work left for them. They realised that they could have created and used an online system to monitor and interact with students and give them live feedback. One area where all eight teachers were successful was their ability to connect physical models to everyday phenomena. They met these criteria, as they addressed physics models concerning everyday situations and their applications in solving problems in real life. I believe that all eight teachers learned and developed new practices,

gained new skills, created new worksheets, designed experiments and simulations for students to perform online and learned to edit video.

5. Conclusion

This study scrutinised the technological challenges faced by lecturers and students. These challenges are accurate, and these two groups had no choice but to adapt to online teaching and learning. Some of the difficulties they faced included a lack of communication, IT issues, doing experiments using virtual physics laboratories and dealing with personal issues and other factors influencing learning. These challenges affected students, lecturers, faculty and departments. Some colleges successfully designed and implemented delivery strategies for physics laboratory courses through online simulations of the experiments. Those who were not ready were unable to conduct live, online demonstrations. But some could post recorded lectures, provide tutorial support, and take advantage of online breakout room sessions to engage students, as stressed by Ametepe and Khan (2021).

Despite the challenges, we have seen how we have coped with the pandemic crisis in the UK and worldwide. We managed to keep on learning and engaging with our students. In a way, we have learned to deal with the pandemic in an educational context and are still learning how to prepare for the next wave, if there is one. Despite the adverse scenarios, this study has shown that overcoming challenges depends on collaboration with stakeholders, teachers, parents, learners, technological companies, and the government.

Undoubtedly, the COVID-19 pandemic has offered us the long-awaited opportunity to figure out and re-imagine the physics teaching experience. Here are the fundamental changes I would like to see implemented or included in any future planning for online physics courses in colleges or further education to create an inclusive learning environment and increase learner engagement:

- The integration of virtual physics laboratory simulations, video laboratories and remote laboratories can play a significant role in the absence of a physical laboratory. The government should invest in them and build a virtual laboratory that can be accessed from anywhere to benefit students.
- To engage students in break-out rooms, emphasise the positive aspects of online learning. Use interactive quizzes and encourage group discussions.
- Create ready-made, high-quality online learning material because the COVID-19 pandemic may be here to stay. We must be prepared for any future issue.
- The study notes that first-year students struggled with online learning. Therefore, more support is needed. I suggest that a blended form of education should be encouraged.
- Students must be encouraged to collect data independently using video recordings or smartphones regarding physics experiments.
- For those offering online recorded videos only, I would advise offering live lectures to talk directly to students and interact with them but with the option of registering for those who have missed or would like to revisit it later. Engage in and create interactive sessions; it is better to use multiple-choice questions, online quizzes, discussions, simulations and peer-to-peer collaboration.
- The other alternative is for colleges to think about giving students a kit to perform experiments, collect data, analyse, get results and send them remotely to their teacher.

- In any recurrence of the pandemic, put educational guidelines from the UK government and awarding bodies in one place so that information is accessible.
- Colleges or the government must ensure that every student has access to remote provisions. For instance, colleges can support students without sufficient remote facilities by providing computers or laptops through a scheme. This can be done in conjunction with the government.
- Technology training is a must for reliable, efficient interactive platforms such as Google Classroom, Office 365 Education (Microsoft Team) etc. Training is vital for teachers and students using software and hardware and should be offered regarding the use of online teaching and learning.
- The issues of safeguarding and online safety should be addressed. Students must be kept safe and trained to protect themselves. Students with SEND and EAL learners must also be supported. Teaching needs to be adapted. For instance, steps must be put in place to ensure learners continue to make progress.
- To keep students motivated and engaged, schools can log participation, motivation, and feedback to share with parents and carers, giving a regular report. Parents should be involved in supporting remote learning. Colleges should keep regular communication with parents through emails or phones.

To sum up, further recommendations for future research along the line of using new technology in artificial intelligence, robotics, and virtual reality (Kang and Seo, 2021, p.35) could provide us with a different viewpoint. Also, other researchers could focus solely on students' experience of online physics teaching. Additionally, one could research online learning platforms and the challenges they have created.

6. References

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